

LOAD FREQUENCY CONTROL OF NONLINEAR INTERCONNECTED HYDRO-THERMAL SYSTEM USING DIFFERENTIAL EVOLUTION TECHNIQUE

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Abstract : This paper presents a differential evolution algorithm to design a robust PI and PID controllers for Load Frequency Control (LFC) of nonlinear interconnected power systems considering the boiler dynamics, Governor Dead Band (GDB), Generation Rate Constraint (GRC). Differential evolution algorithm is employed to search for the optimal controller parameters. The proposed method easily copes of with nonlinear constraints. Further the proposed controller is simple, effective and can ensure the desirable overall system performance. The superiority of the proposed approach has been shown by comparing the results with published fuzzy logic controller for the same power systems. The comparison is done using various performance measures like overshoot, settling time and standard error criteria of frequency and tie-line power deviation following a 1% step load perturbation in hydro area. It is noticed that, the dynamic performance of proposed controller is better than fuzzy logic controller. Sensitivity analysis is performed with wide variation in system parameters. Furthermore, it is also seen that the proposed system is robust and is not affected by change in the system parameters.

Keywords : Load Frequency Control (LFC); Governor Dead Band (GDB); Generation Rate Constraint (GRC); Differential Evolution (DE) algorithm.

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